

Multi-directional pattern repeats – an alternative method for pattern repetition

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Abstract

This paper reports on the development of alternative methods to introduce irregularities in regular repeats systems based on multi-directional pattern repeats explorations. Results from these explorations are used in broadening of teaching methods in pattern repeats to generate new forms of surface pattern configurations. By allowing patterns to repeat in all directions—sideways, upside down, and vertically—the study highlights the creative potential and versatility of this approach in applications like wallpaper and textile prints. The practical methods used in this work combine physical sketching and digital work to test multiple ways to join a pattern repeat.

The main contribution is to develop the art of repeating patterns and to create variety in the pattern image by experimenting with several options for the joint. Another contribution is in-depth knowledge of the field of surface pattern design, and the highlighting of an area that is rarely in focus within design research.

Introduction

There are many components that are important for a successful surface pattern. Pattern design is an artistic skill that requires knowledge and sensitivity of colours, shape, and composition, as well as the technical conditions for production. A basic requirement for a pattern to emerge is *repetition*. When designing, the designer examines what happens to the motif when it is repeated according to a system – repeat patterns. The repetition of shapes across the surface creates both rhythm and dynamics. Harmony and symmetry, direction and flow, scale and proportion, are other concepts that the designer works with.

Pattern designers often aim to conceal the joints between repeats to create a seamless, infinite effect. Repeating joints can also be emphasized and made obvious by letting the motif lie across the width of the fabric, firmly and crosswise (Fig. 1a and b). The choice depends on the desired expression. A well-composed pattern is characterized by an enjoyable movement in the repetition, in addition to a certain degree of complexity. Engaging the viewer's intellect and curiosity, recognize and be challenged by the overall composition adds to the aspect of pleasure. Patterns should offer visual discovery over time—clear up close, yet different from a distance—maintaining interest and avoiding predictability.

Figure 1a and b: Example of a seamless pattern repeat, *Tiara* by Erja Hirvi for Marimekko, 2024 (1a). *Tinnitus* by Elsa Chartin, n.d., showcases a distinct pattern repeat (1b).

Background

Experimenting with pattern joints is nothing new. One of the earliest pioneers was William Morris, who changed surface pattern design with his magical pattern repeats for textiles, wallpaper and carpet designs, amongst other. Morris used geometrical repeats, preferably the mirrored symmetry, to create large-scaled undulating lines to give the impression of growth and movement.¹

Josef Frank is a well-known architect and pattern designer that developed his skills in pattern design by studying Morris' remarkable way of working and became a master of creating dynamic and spectacular patterns.² Frank took repeat pattern design one step further by combining step-repeat and rotation and managed to achieve such intricate patterns that the repeat was hard to discern (Fig. 2).

¹Pevsner, Nikolaus. *Pioneers of modern design: from William Morris to Walter Gropius*. Yale University Press, USA, 2005.

²Wängberg-Eriksson, Kristina. *Pepis flora: Josef Frank som mönsterkonstnär*. Carlsson Publishing, Stockholm, Sweden, 2022.

Figure 2: *Mirakel* by Josef Frank from 1925-30, screen-printed on linen by Ljungbergs Textiltryck for Svenskt Tenn. The pattern unit is half-dropped combined with rotation.

The design studio Timorous Beasties are known for their contemporary take on the historic toiles as well as for their surreal and rebellious aesthetics in textiles and wallpapers.³ Timorous Beasties works unconventionally with repeat patterns and argue that a well-designed surface pattern has to flow and hide the join of the repeat. However, it depends on what surface the pattern is going on, and on its purpose. The pattern *Omni Drips* (Fig. 3) draws aesthetic inspiration from traditional damask designs and is printed 'railroad'—meaning the wallpaper is hung horizontally rather than vertically. This orientation allows the design to be tailored more precisely to the height of the wall.

Figure 3. *Omni drips* by Timorous Beasties, 2013. The wallpaper is printed 'railroad' i.e., height can be altered.

³ Farley, Kate. Repeat Printed Patterns for Interiors. Bloomsbury Publishing Plc, London, Great Britain, 2023.

Repetition in surface patterns

Driven by a fascination with the emotional and spatial impact of pattern repetition, I explore the creative potential within simple pattern repeat structures. This interest forms the foundation of my research in surface pattern design, particularly focusing on how traditional repeating methods can be further developed and reimaged. The main aim here is to establish and to develop an alternative method that introduces irregularity within a regular repeat system. As an experienced textile design teacher, I have observed that students often default to the block repeat system when designing patterns—perhaps out of habit or because it feels more manageable. Therefore, the results from this exploration are used to broaden teaching methods in pattern repeats by exploring repeat rhythms as a way of generating new surface patterns configurations.

Pattern repetition serves multiple purposes: it creates a seamless, continuous surface, allowing small units to cover large areas, and meets manufacturing standards in industries like wallpaper, textiles, and tiles. Aesthetically, repetition enhances visual interest and is fundamental to surface pattern design. Central to this is the joint between units, where geometric order and structural logic play a crucial role in maintaining a sense of order.

Understanding repetition is vital for textile designers, as it enables creative control using methods like half-drop, block, brick, or mirrored repeats. It also allows for adapting patterns to various applications, from flat surfaces to 3D objects. Technical precision and clear communication with manufacturers are essential for working effectively across different industries.

Multi-directional repeats

Historically, repeating patterns with multi-directional method has its origin in wallpaper design⁴, although the method is scarcely outspoken nor established theoretically. The advantages for using this method for wallpaper design are many. Maximum variation is achieved even in a small-scale pattern. This means that the wallpaper can be installed with a tight fit, which in turn reduces paper consumption, saves resources and is easier and more economical for the user.

However, the principle could easily be transferred to textile printing and all kinds of pattern design as such. Straightforwardly, multi-directional repeating could be explained as pattern repetition in all directions; sideways, upside down, and vertically. The repeat is designed so that the pattern unit can link to each other in more places than in traditional repeating. The meeting between the pattern units acts as a passage, or channel; a permissive, or 'tolerant', area in the joints that enables closer convergence between the pattern's figures.

The exploration began with pen and gridded paper to grasp the basics of multi-directional repeats before continuing with digital tools. There is no standard solution for creating these repeats; each pattern requires a unique approach. Designing tile patterns is suggested as a useful way to understand the concept.

A simple motif consisting of four eels swimming freely was designed. For a motif to align seamlessly in all directions, any pattern shapes divided by the paper's edge must be identical

⁴ Korn, Mirjam. *Oregelbundna tapetmönster: Alternativa metoder för mönsterpassning*. Hantverkslaboratoriet, Göteborgs universitet Mariestad, Sweden, 2022.

in size and precisely positioned to ensure a perfect fit when repeated. Half of the eels' body were cut in two and placed in the middle of each side (Fig. 4). It was made sure that the eels had the same thickness (5mm) and positioned in the middle of each side of the paper. The pattern unit was then rotated and multiplied four times, becoming a new unit (Fig. 5).

Figure 4. One unit of Eels in motion.

Figure 5. Four units of Eels in motion.

When rotating the unit (Fig. 5), it was apparent that diverse pattern expressions emerged depending on how the unit was combined. Figure 6 shows how the unit was block-repeated and figure 7 displays another appearance when every second unit is mirrored, rotated and flipped vertically. The initial unit is marked in red.

Fig. 6. The block-repeated pattern unit.

Fig. 7. The unit is mirrored, rotated and flipped

The conclusion that followed the initial experiment was that the measuring points were crucial when placing the pattern motifs. Furthermore, another key insight, and somewhat a confirmation, was about the joint: This is where things happen, this is where the adaption takes place. The middle area, however, is a 'free zone' where the pattern motifs could work independently from any repeat.

The experimentation carried on with a narrow, rectangular shape, similar to that of a wallpaper. Continued with the fish as motif and designed them to be slightly universal, however, some of them was given eyes and a mouth to insinuate a character and also an indication of upside down (Fig. 8a).

Fig. 8a and b. Sketch for Fish in motion (8a) and a detail of the measurements (8b).

Using 5 mm gridded paper, the specified measurements were applied—0.5 cm and 1.5 cm—in intervals, following the sequence: 1.5 – 1.5 – 1.5 – 0.5, repeated four times (Fig. 8b). This created a spacing of 1.5 cm between each fish. Every second fish measured 0.5 cm and 1.5 cm at the midpoint. By cutting the sketch into two halves (Fig. 9a), it was possible to align the fish shapes with each other. The fixed dimensions allowed the design to be step-repeated vertically (Fig. 9b and 9c), as well as in an upside-down arrangement (Fig. 9d).

Fig. 9a

9b

9c

9d. Exploring step-repeats.

Fig. 10. Developed sketch for Fish in motion.

The sketch was modified and developed; filled with more fish and water creatures (Fig. 10). Working by hand made it easier to test the fit of the joints without too much hassle. The computer was used as a tool to make quick and dirty try-outs. Each fish was given a separate colour, however, cut in half for the sake of the joining as well as easy detection (Fig. 11). On the following pages, figs. 12-15 shows different ways of trying out the multi-directional repeat.

Fig. 11. Fish in motion under development.

Figure 12. Using step-repeat makes it easy to understand the repeat construction.

Figure 13. Every second unit is upside down, still displaying an obvious repeat.

Figure 14. (Kind of) Half-drop repeat gives a slightly less detectable order.

Figure 15. Random placed units make it harder to see a clear repetition.

In the middle area of the repeat—unaffected by the edges—pattern motifs can function independently from the joint. In this example, it is the space between the fishes that opens up for variation. More fish was added, all of them in diverse sizes, colours and shapes.

Suddenly, the repeat is nearly impossible to distinguish (Fig. 16). The geometrical “force” that a repeat provides is toned down in favour to a complete sense of freedom. The multi-directional repeat at its best.

Figure 16. Random placed units make it hard to see a clear repeat.

Workshop with students

I decided to explore how multi-directional pattern repetition could be introduced in teaching by conducting a workshop with first-year textile design students. The goal was to assess students' understanding of the concept and its impact on their design outcomes. After a brief introduction and with identical starting materials, gridded paper, pen and pencils, students produced a wide range of results—demonstrating both diversity and a general grasp of the method.

Figure 16 shows how Ellen Johnsson developed her pattern for wallpaper. She investigated different ways of combining the pattern unit, searching for various expressions.

Figure 16. Student work for wallpaper design using the multi-directional repeat system.

Johnsson continued with simple colour experiments to see how she could position the colours to achieve the expression she wanted (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. Colour try-outs.

The process continued by translating the sketches to suggestions of wallpaper design. The design offered many combination possibilities; step-repeat, half-drop repeat, full-drop repeat. (Fig. 18). Here, the pattern unit is seen from the 'right' direction, i.e., the crown is upwards.

Figure 18. Different combinations.

Figure 19. More combinations.

The pattern could also be turned upside down so that the crown points in both directions (Fig. 19). The placement of the colours allows for even greater variations. The alternatives are nearly endless.

The workshop was repeated with third-year textile design students, who quickly began exploring creative applications of the method. One student, Kristina Breitholtz, challenged the conventional rectangular or square repeat format by experimenting with a hexagonal shape as an alternative structure for pattern repetition (Fig. 20).

Figure 20. Sketches on hexagonal shapes.

The third-year students were about to start their degree work, the final project where they decide for themselves what to focus on. Breitholtz was intrigued by the potential of using multi-directional repeats and continued to investigate this in her degree work. Her theme was storytelling and conversational patterns using the narrating qualities in combination with multi-directional repeats. Breitholtz concluded on breaking up the hexagon and used the equilateral triangular shape as is made the pattern expression more varied (Fig. 21).

Figure 21. Sketches on Triangular shape.

The aim of Breitholtz’s work was to design a collection of printed fabrics for interiors that explored conversational patterns and multi-directional repeats, taking inspiration from the mythology of the labyrinth.⁵ Figure 22 shows the first iterations of the pattern Ariadne’s Dance, hand painted and re-worked digitally.

Figure 22. Sketches on Ariadne’s Dance.

Breitholtz worked with layers in the pattern, experimenting with background, textures and motifs. Simultaneously, she tested the repeat to make sure that the distinction between the layers and the edges of the repeat were working (Fig. 23).

Figure 23. Final repeat on Ariadne’s Dance in two colourways.

Figure 24 shows the complete pattern using a multi-directional repeat system, based on a triangular repeat unit. Breitholtz created an overall visual flow in which the composition of individual elements works seamlessly. She thoroughly explored how the motifs behaved in repetition to achieve the desired expression and rhythm. The pattern elements were organized into layers—the grapes, the dancing footprints, the ball of yarn, and the key—each with distinct expressive qualities such as opacity, colour, and scale. By applying different repeat systems to each layer, she was able to create a ‘hidden repeat’ effect. Breitholtz further expanded the system by introducing multiple layers, directions, and colour variations. Finally, the pattern was digital printed on linen in the orange colourway (Fig. 25).

⁵ Breitholtz, Kristina. *The Labyrinth, a labyrinth: An exploration of conversational patterns and multi-directional repeats*. BA thesis. University of Borås, Sweden, 2025.

Figure 24. Final pattern of Ariadne's Dance.

Figure 25. Ariadne's Dance shown hanging from two corners, draped to create a shadow play. The rounded folds underscore the winding expression of the pattern.

Conclusion

This paper explores multi-directional pattern repeats as an alternative way of repeating surface patterns. The aim was to establish and develop an alternative method that introduces irregularity into a regular system, in order to advantage the variations that repetition can offer. The method does not claim to be new or exceptional; rather, its uniqueness lies in how it challenges—or outmanoeuvres—a rigid repeat system. Furthermore, the principle offers a brilliant way of creating movement in a pattern, along with making vivid surfaces or to design motifs with a spectacular effect. The method could also be used if the pattern has several visual 'layers', e.g., a small repetitive pattern in the background and a larger loop of leaves in the foreground. But most of all, it is an excellent and fun challenge for the designer.

The study demonstrates that it is possible to extend the appearance of surface patterns, by expanding the methods for repeat patterns. Breitholtz's work demonstrate that other format of the repeat could be utilised; geometrical shapes like polygons, parallelogram, rhombus, or other irregular shapes. Another technical development would be to include digital software like Blender or Processing, to expand on coding patterns.

The main contribution is to develop the art of repeating patterns and to create variety in the pattern image by experimenting with several options for the joint. Another contribution is in-depth knowledge of the field of surface pattern design, and the highlighting of an area that is

rarely in focus within design research. By undertaking this research, my wish is to raise the status of surface patterns, underline the significance of being a skilled pattern designer, and change the attitude towards patterns. The ability to design a flawless repeating pattern is highly connected to the textile design profession, and should be considered to be a strong, unyielding, and powerful expertise that should be acknowledged.

How would this be relevant to the field of textile design to be further explored? Much of the research carried out in the field of textile design relates to material development and expression-changing materials, but this research seeks to open up for alternative thinking regarding surface pattern design, more specifically on pattern repeats. It is hoped that this work will additionally develop the subject and highlight the importance of designing surface patterns, and the impact that this has on the working process and resulting designs. Surface patterns should not be underestimated—their visual and emotional impact can be powerful and even magical, deserving greater recognition and appreciation.